

Coordination and Solvent Extraction Behaviour of Oxozirconium(IV), Thorium(IV) and Dioxouranium(VI)

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The systematic liquid-liquid extraction behaviour of oxozirconium(IV), thorium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) have been investigated using a number of synthesised and commercial chelating extractants. The synergism or antagonism for these processes in presence of neutral donor ligands have also been identified and the conditions for separation and isolation of pure individual metal ions have been established. The coordination behaviour of oxozirconium(IV), thorium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) with a large number of mono- and polydentate ligands have been studied. With oxozirconium(IV), invariably always a cyclic, tetranuclear species is obtained, derived from the tetrameric structure of the parent $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ which is actually $[Zr_4(OH)_8(H_2O)_{16}]Cl_6 \cdot 12H_2O$. No simple, monomeric oxozirconium(IV) complex was obtained. Uranium(VI) and thorium(IV) form a wide variety of complexes of higher coordination numbers and several bi- and trinuclear complexes were also characterised where the two adjacent metal centres are joined to each other by a double hydroxo-bridge.

THE actinides are an important group of elements. The two earlier members of the actinides, e.g. thorium and uranium, available in large quantities, are relatively inexpensive and their naturally occurring isotopes are fairly easy to handle¹. They find significant use as nuclear fuel. The choice of nuclear fuel and its immediate container (cladding) alongwith the moderator, coolant and controller are all important aspects of nuclear reactors. The low neutron-absorbing character of zirconium coupled with its desirable metallurgical properties make Zr an attractive metal for cladding in nuclear reactor construction. The lanthanide contraction causes Zr and Hf to possess similar chemical properties and they also occur together in nature. Hf has a very high neutron-absorbing propensity (ca. 600 times more so than Zr) and its removal is necessary as nuclear reactors require Hf-free zirconium². The radioactive ⁹⁵Zr ($t_{1/2} = 65$ days, β -emitter) can be extracted from the products of uranium fission and is a useful isotope for Zr tracer studies. Thus, the three elements, Zr, Th and U, are of strategic importance and their isolation, purification and chemistry are of tremendous significance. Solvent extraction methods, taking advantage of the differing solubilities of various salts and complex species in diverse solvent media, provide a neat and efficient method in this regard^{3,4}.

Zr, Th and U exhibit a number of oxidation states, but Zr^{IV} , Th^{IV} and U^{VI} are the most stable and due to their large size (Zr^{4+} , 79 pm; Th^{4+} 102 pm and U^{6+} 80 pm) coupled with their high charge form compounds with a relatively high coordination number of 8 or more, which is certainly higher than is usually encountered for most transition metals⁵. Zr^{IV} has a spherically symmetrical d^0 -configuration and as such no stereochemical

preferences arise from the partly filled d -shell, enabling compounds having a great variety of coordination geometries to be obtained. Ligand field interactions in $5f$ transition element complexes are very small, so that there is little or no contribution to the kinetic stability of the complexes, giving rise to a marked degree of flexibility in the coordination geometries adopted by the actinide elements.

Because of the technical importance of solvent extraction of these three strategic metals and their interesting and versatile coordination behaviour, these two aspects of Zr^{IV} , Th^{IV} and U^{VI} have been actively pursued in the author's laboratory during the past several years. In what follows, a condensed summary of the results of investigations by the author and his coworkers will be discussed under the two section: (i) solvent extraction behaviour and (ii) coordination behaviour of oxozirconium(IV), thorium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI).

Solvent extraction behaviour :

The systematic liquid-liquid extraction behaviour of Zr^{IV} , Th^{IV} and U^{VI} with bidentate Schiff bases, e.g. *N*-salicylidene-*p*-toluidine and *N*-salicylidene-*p*-phenetidine (H-SalA) ($A = p$ -toluidine, *p*-phenetidine), in benzene as the diluent reveals the quantitative extraction of Zr^{IV} at pH ~ 3 and of Th^{IV} at pH ~ 7 , whereas four consecutive extractions seem to be necessary for the quantitative extraction of U^{VI} at pH 6 (Fig. 1). From slope analysis, the nature of the extracted species seem to be $[Zr_4(OH)_8(H_2O)_8(H-SalA)_2]Cl_6$, $Th(H-SalA)Cl_6$ and $[(UO_2)_2(OH)_2(H-SalA)]Cl_2$ and the extraction efficiency follows the order, $Zr^{IV} > Th^{IV} > U^{VI}$. It is thus feasible to separate Zr from Th and U by solvent extraction with H-SalA. Th^{IV} and U^{VI} can be separated using the exchange reaction techniques.

Fig. 1. pH-dependence of extraction of Th^{IV} , U^{VI} and Zr^{IV} from chloride or perchlorate solutions with a tetradentate Schiff base (H_2Sal_2ED) and a bidentate Schiff base extractant ($HSalTol$).

The tetradentate Schiff base ligand, bis(salicylidene)ethylenediamine (H_2Sal_2ED) has also been used as an extractant for the separation of Zr^{IV} , Th^{IV} and U^{VI} by the solvent extraction technique⁸ using benzene as the diluent and the results have been compared with those of the bidentate ligand ($H-SalA$). The results show that the extraction of U^{VI} is significantly improved for (H_2Sal_2ED) as compared to the bidentate $H-SalA$ (A =toluidine). A single extraction at pH 6.5 with H_2Sal_2ED quantitatively extracts U^{VI} . Extraction of all the three metal ions, Zr^{IV} , Th^{IV} and U^{VI} becomes quantitative at pH ~ 6.5 , and the species extracted are suggested to be $[Zr_4(OH)_{12}(H_2Sal_2ED)_2]Cl_2$, $[Th(OH)_8(HSal_2ED)]$ and $[UO_2(OH)(HSal_2ED)]$.

The commercially available chelating extractants, LIX-26 (an alkylated oxine), LIX-54 (a β -diketone derivative) and LIX-84 (an oxime derivative) have also been successfully employed in the solvent extraction of Zr^{IV} , Th^{IV} and U^{VI} . Extraction of Zr^{IV} from dilute HCl medium by 5% LIX-26 results in maximum extraction at 1 M HCl⁹. Addition of thiocyanate greatly enhances the extraction efficiency from dilute HCl solutions. Also, synergism has been observed by a mixture of LIX-26 and a neutral donor, dioctyl sulphoxide (DOSO) from both dilute HCl and thiocyanate media. The extracted species is a monosolvate of DOSO. Extraction of Th^{IV} and U^{VI} increases with increase in pH by 10% (v/v) LIX-26 and with 10% (v/v) n-BuOH

as modifier, the extraction becoming quantitative at pH ~ 5 for U^{VI} , whereas at the same pH only 52.5% extraction is observed for Th^{IV} (Fig. 2). While synergistic extraction of Th^{IV} by mixtures of LIX-26 and DPSO (dipentyl sulphoxide) takes place, antagonism has been established for U^{VI} by the same extractant mixture¹⁰. The extracted species for Th^{IV} and U^{VI} are of the type $[ThQ_2(DPSO)_2(NCS)_2]$ and $[UO_2Q_2(DPSO)]$ (where HQ =LIX-26).

Fig. 2. Influence of pH on extraction of Th^{IV} and U^{VI} by 10% (v/v) LIX-26 and 10% (v/v) n-BuOH in benzene.

The species involved in the solvent extraction of Zr^{IV} from HCl medium by mixtures of thenoyl-trifluoroacetone, HTTA (a β -diketone) and dipentyl sulphoxide (DPSO) in benzene as the diluent seems to be $Zr(OH)_2(TTA)_2(DPSO)^{11}$. The solvent extraction behaviour of the commercial extractant LIX-54 (a β -diketone derivative) has been studied for Zr^{IV} , Th^{IV} and U^{VI} . No appreciable extraction of Zr^{IV} has been observed in the concentration range 0.1–2 M HCl¹² by LIX-54 alone, whereas presence of NCS^- results in appreciable extraction. However, synergism has been observed in the extraction of Zr^{IV} by mixtures of LIX-54 and TBP from thiocyanate media. Similarly, LIX-54 alone does not extract Th^{IV} appreciably¹³ although quantitative extraction of Th^{IV} by a mixture of 10% LIX-54 and 0.1 M tri-n-octyl phosphine oxide (TOPO) in benzene was observed at pH 2.8. A

comparative study on the extraction of U^{VI} by 5% LIX-54 and by a mixture of 5% LIX-54 and TBP in benzene as the diluent in the acidic pH range 0–7 shows that the extraction of UO_2^{II} by a mixture of 5% LIX-54 and 5% TBP becomes quantitative at pH 4.3, while extraction by 5% LIX-54 in benzene passes through a maximum at pH 5.3 ($E_{max}=30\%$). The slope analysis determination using regression analysis suggests the extracted species to be possibly of the type $[Th(TTA)_2(A)_2]$ in case of Th^{IV} and $[UO_2(OH)(A)(HA)(TBP)]$ in case of U^{VI} (where $HA=LIX-54$, $HTTA=$ thenoyl-trifluoroacetone and $TBP=n$ -tributylphosphate).

Quantitative extraction has been observed for U^{VI} by mixtures of the commercial oxime-based extractant LIX-84 and 0.1 M dibenzoylmethane at pH 4.2, although only very little extraction has been observed in case of Th^{IV} by LIX-84 or its mixtures with other neutral donors and chelating extractants.

Synergism has been observed in the extraction of Zr^{IV} by mixtures of a cationic extractant Aliquat-336 (tricapryl methyl ammonium chloride) or Alamine-336 (tricapryl amine) and the neutral donor TBP or DOSO from strong aqueous HCl solutions ($>6M$ HCl)¹⁶. The extracted species are suggested to be $Q_2ZrCl_6 \cdot L$, where $Q=R_3N^+(CH_2)_n$ for Aliquat-336 and $Q=R_3NH$ for Alamine-336 and $L=1BP$ or DOSO. Investigations are under way for the extraction and purification of these metals using other synthesised and commercial chelating extractants.

Coordination behaviour :

Several oxometal compounds of the type MO^{2+} and MO_2^{2+} are found among the early transition elements of groups IV, V and VI and the strongly bound oxygen(s) of these oxyocations provide additional means for studying the complexes. The metal-oxygen multiple bond stretching frequencies appear in the range 900–1100 cm^{-1} for MoO^{2+} , MoO_2^{2+} , WO_2^{2+} , VO^{2+} , and UO_2^{2+} compounds but convincing evidence for mononuclear TiO^{2+} or ZrO^{2+} species in certain so-called titanil or zirconyl compounds are lacking^{17–19}. After examining a number of solid compounds Clearfield²⁰ concluded that the existence of $Zr-O$ multiple bond has not been unequivocally demonstrated, and MacDermott²¹ identified the apical $Zr-O$ bond in K_2ZrO_5 as the only probable example of a $Zr=O$ bond and added that there is no doubt that the ZrO^{2+} group as a persistent species in solution is mythical. Kharitonov and Zaitsev²² suggested the range $\sim 800-1100$ cm^{-1} for $\nu_{Zr=O}$, but also noted that δ_{MOH} deformation mode can give rise to strong bands in the same region. An ir band at 918 cm^{-1} was assigned to $\nu_{Zr=O}$ in $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ ²³, but this was displaced to 697 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 4D_2O$ ²⁴ refuting the claim for the existence of ZrO^{2+} . Further confirmation has come from the Raman spectra of $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ ^{25–27} and no evidence for $\nu_{Zr=O}$ was found. Some polymeric

form of Zr^{IV} predominates both in the solid state^{28,29} and in solution, as evident from the nmr spectral measurements of hydration numbers in solution³⁰. The Zr atoms in $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ lie in a distorted square, linked by pairs of hydroxobridges and also bound to $4H_2O$, so that each Zr atom is coordinated by 8 oxygen atoms in a distorted dodecahedral (D_{2d}) arrangement with $Zr-OH$ (bridging) of 214.2 pm and $Zr-OH_2$ (terminal) of 227.2 pm^{28,29}. However, in spite of this convincing proof, ZrO^{2+} group is said to be present in several complexes of the type $[ZrO(X)_2(L)_2]$ ($X=Cl, Br, NO_3, NCS$): $[ZrO(L)_4]^{2+}$ and $[ZrO(L)_6](ClO_4)_2$, where L represents several oxygen donor ligands^{31–33} and in a number of Schiff base complexes^{37,38} of the type $[ZrO(HL)_2]$, $[ZrOCl(L)]$ and $[ZrO(L)_2]$. A weak ir band in 880–980 cm^{-1} region has been assigned to the $\nu_{Zr=O}$ but the low intensity of these bands argues against such assignment^{39,40}.

In contrast, U forms UO_2^{2+} ion very similar to the other -yl ions, e.g., CrO_2^{2+} , MoO_2^{2+} and WO_2^{2+} . In fact, uranium and other actinides form the actinyl ions, AnO_2^{2+} , where the *trans*-axial O–An bonds are very strong and cannot be protonated and are always shorter than the equatorial bonds. The U–O distance is only 180 pm in UO_2^{2+} group, which is close to that of the $O_3=O$ bond in isostructural $O_3O_2^{2+}$ group (175 pm). Although MoO_2^{2+} is reminiscent of the linear UO_2^{2+} ion, the MoO_2^{2+} has *cis*- and bent structure maximising $O(p_\pi) \rightarrow Mo(d_\pi)$ bonding⁴¹. Also matrix isolation studies have shown that the unstable molecular species ThO_2 , isoelectronic with UO_2^{2+} is strongly bent (O–Th–O angle 122°) and relativistic effect core potential (RECP) calculations ascribe this to back-bonding from 6d orbitals rather than from 5f orbitals in Th, which favours bent rather than linear geometry, the 6p orbitals are not implicated⁴². The collinear $O=U=O$ ($D_{\infty h}$) attaches organic and inorganic ligands in an approximately equatorial plane and forms a wide variety of complexes of high coordination numbers and varying geometries. The Th^{IV} ion, because of its large size and high charge also forms complexes with high coordination numbers and unusual geometries.

With this in the background, a wide variety of coordination complexes of oxozirconium(IV), thorium(IV), and dioxouranium(VI) have been obtained with uni- and bidentate neutral nitrogen donor ligands and a series of bi- and polydentate Schiff base ligands. The Schiff bases are versatile ligands containing 2 to 6 donor sites and are of specific importance, as the chelating ligands as a class dominate the area of higher coordination polyhedra in scope, numbers and in kinetic and thermodynamic stability.

Unidentate ligands: The unidentate nitrogen donor ligands, imidazole, morpholine and their derivatives react with $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ in acetone medium in presence of triethylorthoformate to

form stable white compounds with a high m.p.⁴⁵. The ir and TG measurements as well as analytical data indicate their polymeric formulation in the solid state where the structure is derived from the basic tetrameric dodecahedral structure of the parent $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ formulated as $[Zr_4(OH)_8(H_2O)_{12}]Cl_4$ (1). The unidentate imidazole and morpholine replace some of the coordinated H_2O molecules and also deprotonate some other H_2O molecules forming compounds of the type $[Zr_4(OH)_{12}(H_2O)_{12-n}L_n]Cl_4$

(2), where $n=1$ for $L=1\text{-MeIm}$, 1-EtIm , 1-ViIm , 2-iPrIm , and 2-PhIm ; $n=2$ for $L=Im$, 2-MeIm and 4-MeMorph ; and $n=4$ for $L=Morph$. The TG, DTG and DTA studies show the stepwise loss of H_2O molecules and the ligands forming complex intermediates with rising temperatures. The stoichiometry of the decomposition products is calculated and based on initial decomposition temperature, an order of thermal stability of the complexes has been proposed.

TABLE 1—UNI- AND BIDENTATE NITROGEN DONOR LIGAND COMPLEXES

Ligands(L)*	Complexes
Unidentate .	
1-MeIm, 1-EtIm, 1-ViIm, 2-iPrIm	$[Zr_4(OH)_{12}(H_2O)_{12-n}L_n]Cl_4$
Im, 2-MeIm, 4-MeMorph	$[Zr_4(OH)_{12}(H_2O)_{10}L_2]Cl_4$
Morph	$[Zr_4(OH)_{12}(H_2O)_8L_4]Cl_4$
Bidentate :	
PBH, Bipy, Phen	$[Zr_4(OH)_8(H_2O)_8L_4]X_8$ ($X=Cl^-, NCS^-$) ThL_4X_4 , ($X=Cl^-, NCS^-, NO_3^-$) $[ThL_4](ClO_4)_4$ $[UO_2(L)X_2]$, ($X=Cl^-, I^-, NO_3^-, 0.5 SO_4^{2-}$) $[UO_2(L)_2(NCS)_2]$ $[UO_2(L)_2](ClO_4)_2$
DMPP	$[Zr_4(OH)_8(H_2O)_{14}L]X_8$ ($X=Cl^-, NCS^-$) $[UO_2(L)(NO_3)_2]$ $[UO_2(L)_2(NCS)_2]$

*Me=Methyl, Et=ethyl, Vi=vinyl, iPr=iso-propyl, Im=imidazole, Morph=morpholine, PBH=2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole, Bipy=2,2'-bipyridyl, Phen=1,10-phenanthroline, DMPP=3,6-dimethyl-1-(2'-pyridyl)pyrazole.

TABLE 2—HETEROCYCLIC BIDENTATE SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Ligands(L)*	Complexes
FA .	
A=o-Tol, m-Tol, p-Tol, o-Anis, p-Anis, p-Phen	$[Zr_4(OH)_{12}(H_2O)_{10}(L)]Cl_4$ $Th(L)_4(NO_3)_4$ $Th(L)_4(NCS)_4$ $U(L)_2X_2$, ($X=Cl^-, NCS^-$)
PyAlA :	
A=Anil, o-Tol, m-Tol, p-Tol, o-Anis, p-Anis, p-Phen	$[Zr_4(OH)_{12}(H_2O)_8(L)_2]Cl_4$ $Th(L)_2X_4$, ($X=NCS^-, NO_3^-$) $[UO_2(OH)(L)Cl]_2$
AcPyA :	
A=o-Tol, m-Tol, p-Tol, o-Anis, p-Anis, p-Phen	$[Zr_4(OH)_{12}(H_2O)_{10}(L)]Cl_4$ $Th(L)(NO_3)_4$ $[UO_2(OH)(H_2O)(L)_2Cl]_2$

*FA=Furfurylidenearylamine, PyAlA=2-pyridine carboxaldehydearylimine, AcPyA=2 acetylpyridinearylimine, Tol=toluidine, Anis=anisidine, Phen=phenetidine.

TABLE 3—COMPLEXES OF UO₂^{II} AND ThIV WITH TETRA-, PENTA- AND HEXADENTATE SCHIFF BASE LIGANDS*

$UO_2(L)X_2$	$Th(H_2Sal_2ED)X_4$
L= H_2Sal_2ED , H_2aaED , H_2baED	X= Cl^- , I^- , NCS^- , NO_3^- , $0.5 SO_4^{2-}$
X= Cl^- , I^- , NCS^- , NO_3^- , $0.5 SO_4^{2-}$	
	$Th(H_2aaED)_2X_4$
	X= Cl^- , I^- , NCS^- , NO_3^- , $0.5 SO_4^{2-}$
$UO_2(H_2Sal_2DT)X_2$	$Th(H_2Sal_2DT)X_4$
X= Cl^- , I^- , NO_3^- , $0.5 SO_4^{2-}$	X= Cl^- , I^- , NCS^- , NO_3^-
$UO_2(H_2Sal_2TT)X_2$	$Th(H_2Sal_2TT)X_4$
X= Cl^- , I^- , NCS^- , NO_3^- , $0.5 SO_4^{2-}$	X= Cl^- , I^- , NCS^- , NO_3^-

* H_2Sal_2ED =Bis(salicylidene)ethylenediamine H_2aaED =bis(acetylacetone)ethylenediamine, H_2baED =bis(benzoylacetone)ethylenediamine, H_2Sal_2DT =bis(salicylidene)diethylenetriamine, H_2Sal_2TT =bis(salicylidene)triethylenetetramine.

Bidentate nitrogen donor ligands - the bidentate ligand, 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole (PBH) (3) is structurally similar to 2,2'-bipyridyl (Bipy) and 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen) in containing the grouping $-N=C-C=N-$. With $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$, all these

three ligands form stable, cyclic tetramers $[Zr_4(OH)_8(H_2O)_8(L)_4]X_8$ ($X=Cl, NCS$; $L=PBH, Bipy, Phen$) with each Zr^{IV} having a coordination number of 8. The ir, Raman and nmr (¹H and ¹³C) spectra confirm the structure proposed⁴⁶. PBH also interacts with UO_2^{II} and Th^{IV} to form 6- or 8-coordinate complexes⁴⁷ of the type $[UO_2(PBH)_nX_2]$ (4, 5) ($n=1, X=Cl, I, NO_3, 0.5 SO_4$; $n=2, X=NCS$), $[UO_2(PBH)_3](ClO_4)_2$ (6) and

○ Uranyl group $O_I=U=O_{II}$ with U atoms in plane of paper and oxygen atoms 1.91 Å above and below this plane

$[Th(PBH)_2X_4]$ ($X=Cl, NCS, NO_3$) or $[Th(PBH)_4(ClO_4)_4]$. The chloro-complexes exhibit ν_{M-Cl} at 245 and 248 cm^{-1} for the UO_2^{VI} and Th^{IV} complexes, respectively, indicating direct M-Cl bond. U^{VI} achieves a higher coordination number in the isothiocyanato-complexes as compared to the halo-complexes. The NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} are bonded in a bidentate fashion while the ClO_4^- remains ionic. These complexes do not exhibit peaks in the mass spectrum that may be assigned to the complex or its metallated fragmentation products (Fig. 3). The TG measurements indicate the relative order of stability of the complexes to be $Cl \approx SO_4 > NO_3 > NCS > I$. The bidentate nitrogen donor ligand, 3,5-dimethyl-1-(2'-pyridyl)pyrazole (DMPP), forms $UO_2(DMPP)_nX_2$ ($n=1, X=NO_3$; $n=2, X=NCS$) as evidenced from 1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra and the mass spectra⁴⁸, while with oxozirconium(IV), $[Zr_4(OH)_8(H_2O)_{14}(DMPP)]X_8$ ($X=Cl, NCS$) complexes are obtained⁴⁹.

Bidentate Schiff base ligands: The bidentate Schiff bases, salicylidenealdimine (H-SalA) obtained from salicylaldehyde and aniline or substituted-aniline (A=aniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine, *o*-phenetidine and *o*- or *p*-chloroaniline),¹ interact

Fig. 3. Mass spectrum of 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole (PBH).

with oxozirconium(IV) salts to form again the cyclic tetramers, $[Zr_4(OH)_8(H_2O)_8(H-SalA)_4]X_8$ ($X=Cl, NCS$)⁴⁹ and with the actinides, the complexes of the type $UO_2(H-SalA)_2X_2$ ($X=Cl, I, NCS, NO_3, 0.5 SO_4$)⁴⁹ and $[Th(H-SalA)_2X_4]$ ($X=Cl, I, NO_3, NCS$)⁵⁰. The *N*-furfurylidenearylamines (FA) form $[Zr_4(OH)_{12}(H_2O)_{12-n}(FA)_n]Cl_4$ ⁵¹, $[UO_2(FA)_2X_2]$ ^{52,53} and $[Th(FA)_nX_4]$ ⁵⁴ (A=substituted-anilines as above; $X=NO_3, n=2$; $X=NCS, n=2$ or 3) complexes.

The bidentate heterocyclic aldimines (PyAlA) and ketimines (AcPyA) obtained from aniline (or substituted-anilines) and 2-pyridine carboxaldehyde or 2-acetylpyridine, form novel dimeric $[UO_2(OH)(PyAlA)Cl]_2$ (7) and $[UO_2(OH)(H_2O)(AcPyA)O_5Cl]_2$ (8) complexes⁵⁵, respectively, where each U^{VI} has a pentagonal bipyramidal structure with two pentagonal rings sharing the two hydroxyl groups. From their TG results, the kinetics of thermal

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decomposition have been investigated for the deligation process and the energy of activation has been determined. The same ligands form $\text{Th}(\text{L})\text{X}_4$ ($\text{L}=\text{PyAlA}$, AcPyA ; $\text{X}=\text{NO}_3$, NCS) complexes⁵⁶. They interact with $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to form tetranuclear compounds⁵⁷ with 4 double-hydroxo-bridges of the composition $[\text{Zr}_4(\text{OH})_{12}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8(\text{PyAlA})_4]\text{Cl}_4$ and $[\text{Zr}_4(\text{OH})_{12}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{10}(\text{AcPyA})_4]\text{Cl}_4$, respectively.

The potential terdentate ligand, 2-amino-4-methylpyridine salicylidimine (HAMPSal), essentially functions as a bidentate one (NO donor set) to form the complexes⁵⁸ $\text{UO}_2(\text{HAMPSal})_2\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$, I , NCS , NO_3 , 0.5SO_4) which are all 8-coordinated. Using $\text{UO}_2(\text{OAc})_2$, the neutral complex $\text{UO}_2(\text{AMPSal})_2$ is obtained⁵⁹. Similar observation has been made for the ligand, *o*-aminophenol salicylideneimine (H_2AphSal), which in spite of its three donor sites (NO_2) functions as a bidentate ligand⁵⁹ forming the neutral complex $\text{UO}_2(\text{H-AphSal})_2$.

Tridentate Schiff base ligands: The tridentate glycyalsalicylideneimine (glySal) and glycyalacetoneimine (glyaa) form neutral complexes⁵⁹, $\text{UO}_2 \cdot \text{L} \cdot \text{xH}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{L}=\text{glySal}$, $\text{x}=1$; $\text{L}=\text{glyaa}$, $\text{x}=2$) containing 6- or 7-coordinate U^{VI} . The orange-red tridentate ligand anthranilicacidsalicylideneimine ($\text{H}_2\text{-AnthSal}$) forms $\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_2\text{-AnthSal})\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$, I , NCS , NO_3 , ClO_4) and with $\text{UO}_2(\text{OAc})_2$ yields the neutral $\text{UO}_2(\text{H-AntSal})_2$ complex, while with Th^{IV} the complexes formed are $\text{Th}(\text{H-AntSal})_2\text{X}_2 \cdot \text{nH}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{n}=2, 3, 4$; $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$, I , NCS , NO_3 , ClO_4)⁶⁰.

Tetradentate Schiff base ligands: A series of dioxouranium(vi)⁵⁹ and thorium(iv)⁶⁰ complexes have been obtained with the tetradentate ligands, bis(salicylidene)ethylenediamine ($\text{H}_2\text{Sal}_2\text{ED}$), bis(β -diketoneimine)ethylenediamine (H_2aaED , H_2baED ;

$\text{aa}=\text{acetylaceton}$, $\text{ba}=\text{benzoylaceton}$, $\text{ED}=\text{ethylenediamine}$). The complexes are of the type $\text{UO}_2(\text{L})\text{X}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{H}_2\text{Sal}_2\text{ED}$, H_2aaED , H_2baED ; $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$, I , NO_3 , NCS , 0.5SO_4), $\text{UO}_2(\text{L})$ (with $\text{UO}_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$), $\text{Th}(\text{L})\text{X}_4$ or $\text{Th}(\text{L})_2\text{X}_4$. The coordination number for U^{VI} is 6 or 8, and for Th^{IV} 8 or 12.

Another tetradentate ligand, *N,N'*-ethylenediamine-bis(isonitrosoethylmethylketoneimine) ($\text{H}_2\text{-DMED}$), obtained by the condensation of biacetylmonoxime and ethylenediamine, forms rather novel

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dinuclear complexes, $[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2\text{X}_2(\text{H}_2\text{-DMED})]$ (9) ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$, NCS)⁶¹, where the two U^{VI} centres are joined by a double-hydroxo-bridge, similar to that in the dinuclear⁶² $[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ and $[\{\text{ThX}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8\}_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2\text{DMED}]$ ($\text{X}=\text{I}$, NCS , NO_3) complexes⁶³. In the latter complexes, the coordination number around each Th^{IV} is satisfied in addition to the double-hydroxo-bridge by the two N donor sites of DMED, two anions and three H_2O molecules giving rise to a coordination number of 9 for the iodo- and thiocyanato-complexes and 11 for the nitrate-complexes. A higher coordination number for the nitrate-complexes is well explained since the nitrate group has a short bite of approximately 2.1 Å only⁶⁴. A coordination number of 11 is well authenticated for $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ^{65,66} and also for a very similar binuclear complex $\text{Th}_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8$ ⁶⁷ where a double-hydroxo-bridge has been established on the basis of X-ray crystal structure determinations.

Pentadentate Schiff base ligands: The linear pentadentate Schiff base, bis(salicylidene)amino-diethylenetriamine ($\text{H}_2\text{Sal}_2\text{DT}$) ($\text{DT}=\text{diethylenetriamine}$), under appropriate conditions gives complexes⁶⁸ of the type $\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_2\text{Sal}_2\text{DT})\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$, I , NO_3 , 0.5SO_4) and $\text{Th}(\text{H}_2\text{Sal}_2\text{DT})\text{X}_4$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$, I , NCS , NO_3) where the ligand is a neutral molecule. However, with $\text{UO}_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ or $\text{Th}(\text{ClO}_4)_4$, the

 TABLE 4—COMPLEXES OF UO_2^{VI} AND Th^{IV} WITH TETRA-, PENTA- AND HEXADENTATE OXIME-BASED SCHIFF BASE LIGANDS*

$[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2\text{X}_2(\text{H}_2\text{DMED})]$ $\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-, \text{NCS}^-$	$[\{\text{ThX}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8\}_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{DMED})]$ $\text{X}=\text{I}^-, \text{NCS}^-, \text{NO}_3^-$
$[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2\text{X}_2(\text{H}_2\text{DMDT})]$ $\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-, \text{NCS}^-$	$[\{\text{ThX}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8\}_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{DMDT})]$ $\text{X}=\text{I}^-, \text{NCS}^-, \text{NO}_3^-$
$[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2\text{X}_2(\text{H}_2\text{DMTT})]$ $\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-, \text{NCS}^-$	$[\{\text{ThX}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8\}_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{DMTT})]$ $\text{X}=\text{I}^-, \text{NCS}^-, \text{NO}_3^-$

* $\text{H}_2\text{DMED}=\text{N,N}'\text{-Ethylenediamine-bis(isonitrosoethylmethylketoneimine)}$, $\text{H}_2\text{DMDT}=\text{N,N}'\text{-N,N}'\text{-diethylenetriamine-bis(isonitrosoethylmethylketoneimine)}$, $\text{H}_2\text{DMTT}=\text{N,N}'\text{-N,N}'\text{-triethylenetetramine-bis(isonitrosoethylmethylketoneimine)}$.

ligand acts as a deprotonated, dinegative anion forming 7-coordinate $UO_2(\text{Sal}_2\text{DT})$ and the 9-coordinate $\text{Th}(\text{Sal}_2\text{DT})(\text{ClO}_4)_2$. In the latter complex, the ClO_4^- acts as a bidentate ligand.

The potential pentadentate ligand, N,N,N' -diethylenetriamine-bis(isonitrosoethylmethylketoneimine) ($H_2\text{DMDT}$) essentially functions as a tetradentate ligand and forms dinuclear $[(UO_2)_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2X_2(H_2\text{DMDT})]^{2+}$ (10) and $[\{\text{Th}X_4(H_2O)_3\}_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2(\text{DMDT})]^{2+}$ complexes, very similar to the analogous $H_2\text{DMED}$ complexes, where the U^{VI}

An extension of the tetradentate $H_2\text{DMED}$ and pentadentate $H_2\text{DMDT}$ ligands, obviously leads to the hexadentate $H_2\text{DMTT}$, the N,N,N',N'' -triethylenetetramine-bis(isonitrosoethylmethylketoneimine), obtained by reacting biacetylmonoxime and triethylenetetramine in 2:1 ratio. Just as in the pentadentate DMDT ligand, this ligand also behaves as a tetradentate ligand, leaving two potential ligating atoms (the secondary amine N's) uncoordinated. The complexes obtained are of the type $[(UO_2)_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2X_2(H_2\text{DMTT})]$ (13) where the U^{VI} centres

achieves a coordination number of 7 and Th^{IV} a coordination number of 9 (for I^- and NCS^-) or 11 (for NO_3^-), through the formation of a double-hydroxo-bridge between the two metal ion centres.

Hexadentate Schiff base ligands: The ligand $H_2\text{Sal}_2\text{TT}$ (11) (TT=triethylenetetramine) on reaction with UO_2X_2 or $\text{Th}X_4$ loses one molecule of

at the sides have a coordination number of 7 with the central U^{VI} being six-coordinated²¹. With $\text{Th}X_4$ ($X=\text{I}, \text{NCS}, \text{NO}_3$), the complex formed are of the type $[\{\text{Th}X_4(H_2O)_3\}_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2(\text{DMTT})]$ (14) with a double-hydroxo-bridge. With $X=\text{I}, \text{NCS}$,

salicylaldehyde from the 3- and 4-positions and forms very stable complexes²⁹ of the type $UO_2(H_2\text{Sal}_2\text{TT})X_2$ (12) ($X=\text{Cl}, \text{I}, \text{NO}_3, \text{NCS}, 0.5 \text{SO}_4$) and $\text{Th}(H_2\text{Sal}_2\text{TT})X_4$ ($X=\text{Cl}, \text{I}, \text{NO}_3, \text{NCS}$). However, with $UO_2(\text{OAc})_2$, a neutral complex of the type $UO_2(\text{HSal}_2\text{TT})$ seems to be formed.

the stereochemistry around each Th has a 9-coordinate structure and with $X=\text{NO}_3^-$; the coordination number is enhanced to 11 due to the small bite³ of the bidentate nitrate group.

Conclusion: The solvent extraction behaviour of Zr^{IV} , Th^{IV} and U^{VI} with a large series of extracting agents have been studied under a wide variety of conditions and the conditions for the extraction of pure metals have been established. The interaction of oxozirconium(IV), thorium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) with a series of mono- and polydentate ligands gives rise to a series of complexes with diverse geometries and higher coordination numbers, a phenomenon that is relatively rare in transition metal chemistry. A comparison of this work with other actinides seems to have a very promising future.

Acknowledgement

The author takes this opportunity for expressing gratitude to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for generous grants for this work and to many friends in Germany and Sweden for the C, H, N microanalysis, FTIR, NMR (^1H and ^{13}C) and mass spectra. The author is also immensely thankful to his very able coworkers, Dr. V. Chakravorty, Dr. H. N. Mohanta, Dr. C. R. Panda, Mr. S. C. Nayak, Miss S. Singh and Mr. P. K. Mishra for their very sincere efforts and valuable contributions without which this work would not have been possible.

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